

Retraction

Retraction: Adyel et al. Health Risk Assessment of Pesticide Residues via Dietary Intake of Market Vegetables from Dhaka, Bangladesh. *Foods* 2013, 2, 64–75

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The following article: doi: 10.3390/foods2010064, available online at: <http://www.mdpi.com/2304-8158/2/1/64> [1], has been retracted by the authors because of some major errors in the broad field of identifying pesticide residue and its concentration. During random cross-check, retention time of pesticides by HPLC did not match with the standard values. As a result, the concentrations of all detected pesticides, maximum residue limits (MRLs), and health risk assessments were altered. These errors render the article [1] incorrect. All authors have confirmed that the reported results were produced using quite inappropriate procedures. As first author, I take full responsibility for the retraction and any other errors in its contents, and would like to offer my apologies on behalf of my co-authors to the readership of *Foods* for any inconvenience caused by this retraction.

Reference

1. Hossain, M.S.; Hossain, M.A.; Rahman, M.A.; Islam, M.M.; Rahman, M.A.; Adyel, T.M. Health risk assessment of pesticide residues via dietary intake of market vegetables from Dhaka, Bangladesh. *Foods* **2013**, *2*, 64–75.

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